

HYDROXYKETONES. PART VI. THE FRIES REARRANGEMENT OF THE PHENOLIC ESTERS OF *o*- AND *m*-NITROBENZOIC ACIDS AND SOME THIOPHENYL ESTERS

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The Fries migrations of *o*- and *m*-nitrobenzoic acid esters with phenol, isomeric cresols and naphthols have been studied. The esters of *m*-nitrobenzoic acid afforded normal migration products while the reaction failed with the esters of *o*-nitrobenzoic acid. This behaviour could be explained due to the absence of complex formation at the phenoxy oxygen, which is sterically hindered.

The migrations of thiophenyl acetate and benzoate were also tried, but without any success.

In continuation of our earlier work (Saharia and Sharma, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, **14B**, 263), the present communication deals with the Fries migrations of the esters of *o*- and *m*-nitrobenzoic acids with phenol, isomeric cresols and naphthols. The compounds thus prepared are expected to be bactericides.

The important observation made during the course of this study was that only the esters of *m*-nitrobenzoic acid furnished normal migration products while those of *o*-nitrobenzoic acid failed to rearrange. This difference is intelligible only if the mechanism of the Fries reaction is closely examined. The generally accepted view at present is that the reaction takes place through a complex formation of the type (I) (Dewar, "The Electronic Theory of Organic Chemistry", Oxford University Press, 1949, p. 230; Lunder and Zuffanti, "The Electronic Theory of Acids and Bases", John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1946, p. 123; Baltzly *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 4192; 1955, **77**, 2522; Sharma, M.Sc. Thesis, Panjab University, 1954).

In the case of the esters of *o*-nitrobenzoic acid (III), a complex formation of the type (I) is hindered by the nitro group which overshadows the phenoxy oxygen atom, while with the esters of *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzoic acids no such hindrance is possible as normal migration products have been isolated in the latter cases.

TABLE I
[NB denotes *m*-nitrobenzoate]

Ester...	M.P.	Cryst. shape.	Solvent.	Yield.	Formula.	% Carbon. Found. Calc.	% Hydrogen, Found. Calc.
A. Phenyl-NB	100°	Colorless prisms.	Dilute alcohol.	63%	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₄ N	64.1 64.2	3.6 3.7
B. <i>p</i> -Cresyl-NB	78°	Shining colorless leaflets.	Alcohol.	66	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₄ N	65.2 65.4	4.5 4.3
C. <i>m</i> -Cresyl-NB	68°	Colorless plates.	"	70	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₄ N	65.3 65.4	4.2 4.3
D. <i>o</i> -Cresyl-NB	101-102°	Colorless prisms.	Dilute alcohol	64	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₄ N	65.1 65.4	4.2 4.3
E. α -Naphthyl-NB	109°	Colorless plates.	Alcohol-acetone.	53	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₄ N	70.0 69.6	3.5 3.8
F. β -Naphthyl-NB	138° (Lit. 134°)	Light brown shining leaflets.	"	80	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₄ N	...	...

TABLE II
[N- denotes 3'-nitrobenzophenone]

* Ester.	Ketone.	M.P.	Cryst. shape.	Solvent.	Yield.	Formula.	% Carbon. Found. Calc.	% Hydrogen, Found. Calc.	3:4-Digitro- phenyl hy- drazone in p.
A.	(a) 4-Hydroxy-N	173°	Colorless needles.	Dilute alcohol.	32.5%	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₄ N	...	...	210°
	(b) 2-Hydroxy-N	(lit. 173°) 101°	Yellow needles.	Pet. ether (60°-80°)	5.0	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₄ N	64.2 64.0	3.9 3.7	238-9°
B.	2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-N	104-105°	Bright yellow leaflets.	Dilute alcohol.	62.5	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₄ N	65.2 65.4	4.5 4.3	326°
C.	(a) 2-Methyl-4-hydroxy-N	200°	Dark brown needles.	Benzene.	10.0	"	65.5 65.4	4.4 4.3	—
	(b) 2-Hydroxy-4-methyl-N	132°	Bright yellow needles.	Pet. ether (60°-80°)	15.0	"	65.5 65.4	4.3 4.3	248-9°
D.	(a) 3-Methyl-4-hydroxy-N	182-83°	Tiny colorless needles.	Dilute alcohol.	15.0	"	65.2 65.4	4.2 4.3	233-4°
	(b) 2-Hydroxy3-methyl-N	115°	Bright yellow needles.	Pet. ether (60°-80°)	7.5	"	65.2 65.4	4.4 4.3	—
E.	1-Hydroxynaphthyl (2)-3-nitrophenyl ketone	168°	"	"	20.0	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₄ N	69.6 69.6	4.0 3.8	264°
F.	2-Hydroxynaphthyl-(1)-3-nitrophenyl ketone	160°	Shining yellow plates.	Pet. ether (60°-80°) and benzene.	25.0	"	69.4 69.6	3.8 3.8	—

* Vide Table I

If the complex formation of the type (II); as advocated by other workers (Ralston *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1940, 5, 645, 2169; 1941, 6, 751; Amin and Shah, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1948, 17, Part III, 352; Illare, *Gazzetta*, 1948, 77, 339, 352), is important for the rearrangement, the esters of the type (III) should have furnished the normal reaction products. In absence of any such products the importance of the complex formation (if any) for the Fries reaction at the carbonyl oxygen atom is completely ruled out.

The experimental procedure adopted for the preparation of the esters, their migrations and working up of the products was similar to the one followed earlier (Saharia and Sharma, *loc. cit.*).

In the case of the esters of *o*-nitrobenzoic acid, though varied reaction conditions, such as the use of different solvents, temperatures and quantities of aluminium chloride, were employed, the desired products could not be obtained. The esters were recovered unchanged at lower temperatures while at higher temperatures the reaction mixture became charred.

Keeping in view the acid-base relationship of aluminium chloride and ester in the Fries reaction, it was proposed to study the migrations of thiophenolic esters. Accordingly, thiophenyl acetate and benzoate were prepared and subjected to the Fries reaction, but it did not proceed; most of the ester was recovered unchanged, while a considerable portion got decomposed (cf. Tarbell *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 1668). This difference in behaviour could only be explained on the basis that the sulphur atom has got a larger atomic volume, and hence, a loose control on its valency electrons. It is possible that aluminium chloride forms a complex with the sulphur atom, yet it may not be strong enough to detach the carbonium ion ($R.CO^+$) to afford the rearranged products.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of o- and m-Nitrobenzoic Acid Esters.—The acid chloride (Vogel, "Practical Organic Chemistry", Longman Green & Co., New York, 1948, p. 751) (1M) and the phenols (1M) were thoroughly mixed by shaking in alkaline medium and cooled. The solid esters so obtained were crystallised.

Fries Rearrangement.—The ester (1M) was intimately mixed with $AlCl_3$ (anhyd., 1.3M) in a round-bottomed flask (100 c.c.) fitted with a guard tube and the reaction was carried out at 120° and 160° in an oil-bath for 2 hours. The reaction product was hydrolysed with crushed ice and HCl (dil.) and then extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed free of any acid and then extracted with sodium carbonate (5%) and sodium hydroxide (2%), which on acidification deposited the *para* and *ortho*-hydroxyketones respectively. The residual ethereal solution was worked up for any unchanged ester.

The *o*-hydroxyketones developed violet or dark red coloration with ferric chloride. The ketones were characterised through their 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones. The esters and the ketones are described in Tables I and II.

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